

Role of Co-ordination Complexes in Biological Processes*

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While appreciating the honour of being called upon to deliver the J. C. Ghosh Memorial Lecture of the Society, I cannot but experience a feeling of sadness from the awareness of the fact that the country, and Bengal in particular, was deprived of Dr. Ghosh's dynamic service at a time when it was needed most. The Indian Chemical Society too lost one of its most distinguished Past Presidents, who played a prominent part in the initiation and development of the Society. Scientific education and scientific research in the country today, in spite of all efforts by the Government with provision of generous grants in the budget for the purpose, is in a rather unhappy and unsettled state. Random and repeated *ad hoc* remedial measures have failed to make any improvement. The need for the wise counsel and the constructive approach of a scientific administrator and organizer of the eminence of Dr. Ghosh was never so keenly felt as under the present circumstances. All these thoughts arise crowding in my mind on this occasion in a disquieting manner.

Though called away at a rather early age from active laboratory work to responsible administrative duties, Dr. Ghosh succeeded in leaving a brilliant record of his research work and in building up an active and flourishing school of physical chemistry, many of whose members are now holding quite high positions in the universities and scientific or industrial institutes of the country.

Dr. Ghosh started his scientific career with researches in electrochemistry, which led to the formulation of the well-known Ghosh's law of strong electrolytes, based on the assumption of complete dissociation. This brought him name and fame while he was quite young. The hypothesis, which had to face severe criticisms for its failure to provide satisfactory agreement with experimental results, received later on an exact quantitative formulation by Debye and Hückel.

In his researches on the photochemical action of polarised light on racemic mixtures, Ghosh investigated early in 1926 the problem of asymmetric synthesis, which puzzled the scientists for a long time, but he could not obtain any positive results. The problem was, however, solved a few years later in a similar reaction by Kuhn and Braun. Ghosh and his pupils made also an intensive study of many photochemical reactions, dealing particularly with photo-bromination.

He was furthermore interested in the catalytic production of gaseous fuels as well as in the catalytic synthesis of higher paraffins from water gas. The work on the synthesis

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of organic compounds of industrial importance in India, using various contact catalysts and high pressure technique, was in fact initiated by him.

Redox reactions in biological systems also attracted his attention and a number of publications was made by him and his pupils on the subject.

Dr. Ghosh's interest in chemical reactions in biological systems has prompted me to choose "The Role of Co-ordination Complexes in Biological Processes" as an appropriate subject for a lecture in honour of his memory. Though I cannot claim any special knowledge of this aspect of the chemistry of co-ordination complexes, still I consider it worthwhile to present a summarised account of the work relating to the salient features of the subject, which in recent years has engaged the attention of many workers in the U.S.A. and the U.K., and promises to yield results of fundamental significance and of far reaching consequence. My purpose is to stimulate the interest of the Indian workers in this fascinating aspect of co-ordination chemistry, which is likely to yield a very good dividend if pursued with zeal and determination. For this, however, a team work among the inorganic chemists, the biochemists, and even the biologists and the physiologists might be necessary. It needs hardly be pointed out that science has now reached a stage where isolated efforts by individual specialists can seldom break any new ground of real value.

ROLE OF CO-ORDINATION COMPLEXES IN BIOLOGICAL PROCESSES

The presence of approximately thirty-eight naturally occurring elements has been detected in living bodies. Of these, the number of those, essential to the nutrition of plants and animals, is known to be about twenty to twenty-two. Those, which occur in high or fairly high concentrations, include the following:

Carbon	Calcium	Sodium
Oxygen	Phosphorus	Chlorine
Hydrogen	Potassium	Magnesium
Nitrogen	Sulphur	Iron

The rest are usually present in extremely small quantities and are termed trace elements or minor elements. Of these trace elements, manganese, copper, iodine, fluorine, cobalt, and zinc have been found to be essential to animal life, while the plants require, in addition to copper, manganese, and zinc, elements like boron, molybdenum, vanadium, and in certain cases also aluminium and barium. The functions or usefulness of the remaining trace elements in biological systems remain still unexplored.

Most of the essential metals, excepting sodium, potassium, and to a certain extent calcium, cannot occur in the biological systems in the form of free metal ions, as under the prevailing pH conditions of the systems, these would hydrolyse and separate as precipitates. These must therefore be present in the systems, or transported, as co-ordination complexes or metal chelate compounds. Some of these complexes can be isolated in the free state in a more or less pure state, like hemoglobin, myoglobin, hemocyprein, cyanocobalamin (vitamin B₁₂), cytochrome c, chlorophyll, etc. Evidence for the presence of others, or their formation as intermediate products taking part in the metabolic processes of the living systems, has been obtained from a study of the catalytic action of enzymes.

In the biological systems proteins are mostly found in close association with metallic cations. Because of the presence of many reactive donor groups in the side chain of large protein molecules, the metallic cations, which are incapable of existing in the free state at the comparatively high pH condition of the biological systems, enter into more or less strong complex formation with the protein molecules. The study of these metal-protein complexes and their function in biological systems has emerged as a problem of great significance in biochemistry. The formation, properties, and structure of these metal-protein complexes and their variation with the nature of the metal ion constitute as well an equally important problem of theoretical interest in inorganic chemistry. To the protein chemists the study of these complexes also serves as a valuable aid in the difficult task of unravelling the highly complicated structure of protein molecules.

The metal-protein complexes occurring in nature may be divided broadly into two classes: One in which the metal atom forms an integral part of the protein molecule from which it cannot be removed without destroying the structure of the molecule itself; these proteins are known as *metalloproteins*. In the other class of metal-protein complexes, the metal ion is reversibly bound to the protein molecule, stabilising possibly certain configurations (helical or folded) of the protein molecule. Many enzyme proteins belong to this second category.

Generally, the co-ordination complexes may be said to play two significant roles in the biological systems:

I. They may act as catalysts in many metabolic processes of the living bodies which involve:

- (a) Redox reactions with change in the valency of the metal in the complex.
- (b) Reactions of the acid-base type in which the metal acting as the Lewis acid can combine with a substrate to accelerate a reaction. In these, the metal functions in the form of a labile co-ordination complex as an intermediate in the reaction, the completion of which depends on the decomposition of the complex thus formed.

II. They can serve the purpose of storage and transfer of either metal ions or donor molecules and can function as agents for the transmission of energy in the animal and plant metabolism.

I. Co-ordination Complexes as Catalysts in Metabolic Processes

Reactions in biological systems, i.e., in animal and plant metabolism, are generally enzymatic reactions which mean that they are initiated by specific enzymes acting as catalysts. In fact, biochemical catalysts are called enzymes. The specific compound or group of compounds, whose chemical transformation is initiated by the enzymes, are known as their substrates. Enzymes generally consist of a protein portion as its major constituent and of a non-protein portion which is called prosthetic group of the enzyme. Some enzymes fail to function in the absence of certain simpler organic molecules which are termed co-enzymes. It is, however, difficult to distinguish between co-enzymes and prosthetic groups of an enzyme. In the prosthetic group of many enzymes, there occurs a co-ordinatively

bound metal atom, essential to the functioning of these enzymes. The metal may be bound to the functional or donor atoms of the prosthetic part, as well as of the protein part of the enzyme molecule. It has now been demonstrated from specific studies of metal-enzyme systems that the metal atom forms the centre of reactivity of the enzyme as it acts on its substrate.

(a) Redox Reactions

The role of co-ordination complexes in biochemical redox reactions is of fundamental importance. It provides for the specificity of the oxidant towards a particular substrate, as the redox potential of a metal ion undergoes a wide variation by complex formation with ligands having different donor groups and as the metal in the complex can further co-ordinate with functional groups in the substrate.

The enzyme oxidants containing the metal complex can act directly upon the substrate or indirectly through oxygen molecule for which it acts as a carrier.

Examples of some common oxidation-reduction enzymes are given by ascorbic acid oxidase, peroxidases and catalases, cytochrome oxidases, and those containing sulphhydryl groups of cysteine or glutathione molecule.

It is interesting to refer in this connection to the work of Dr. J. C. Ghosh and his co-workers¹, who described a method for the determination of oxidation-reduction potential of biological systems like ascorbic acid, cysteine, and glutathione. They also investigated the autoxidation of ascorbic acid, its inhibition by sulphur compounds with -SH and -S-S- groupings, and the catalytic effect of Cu (I) and Cu(II) on the system.

The Copper Enzyme Ascorbic Acid Oxidase.—The mechanism of oxidation in this system, studied by Dawson², can be represented by the following scheme:

¹ Ghosh and Ganguli, *Biochem. Z.*, 1935, 279, 296; Ghosh and Rakshit, *ibid.*, 1936, 269, 15; Ghosh and Guha, *this Journal*, 1937, 14, 721.

² Dawson, "The Copper Protein, Ascorbic Acid Oxidase", in "Copper Metabolism", edited by McElroy and Glass, Johns Hopkins Press, Baltimore, 1950.

The action of other oxidases may be represented in a similar manner. The above mechanism for the enzymatic oxidation of ascorbic acid is based on the observations that, unlike its oxidation by copper ion alone, no hydrogen peroxide is formed in this case and hence less oxygen is required for the purpose of oxidation.

Peroxi-dases and Catalases.—These two groups of redox enzymes differ from ascorbic acid oxidase and the similar phenol oxidases by their having porphyrine prosthetic groups with iron as their metallic constituent. The nature of the protein component, however, differs in the two types. Both the types catalyse the degradation of hydrogen peroxide into water and oxygen, and prevent its accumulation in the system as a byproduct of other enzymatic oxidations. For, hydrogen peroxide must be rapidly destroyed in view of its high toxicity. Catalases can oxidise many primary and secondary alcohols at the expense of hydrogen peroxide, whereas peroxidases can similarly bring about *via* hydrogen peroxide the oxidation of a number of substances like diphenols, aminophenols, diamines, etc.

In both these types of enzymes, iron is present as iron(III) in the form of protoporphyrine complexes which show a higher degree of stabilisation in catalases than in peroxidases. The two types also differ in the number of prosthetic groups in their molecules, there being only one such group in a molecule of peroxidase and four such in a molecule of catalase³. The structure of the complex in peroxidase is shown in the following diagram; the structure of protoporphyrine, which is well known, is also shown here for convenience of comparison:

In the peroxidase complex the iron(III) atom, in addition to its attachment to the four nitrogen atoms of the protoporphyrine part of the enzyme molecule, is also coordinated with a carboxyl group of the protein which is at the same time linked at one point with one of the propionic acid side chains of the porphyrine. The sixth coordination position of the iron atom is occupied by a water molecule, which is replaced by hydrogen peroxide during catalysis. Magnetic measurements indicate that in peroxidase the metal-ligand bonds are ionic (with five unpaired electrons), but a transition to the covalent type (one unpaired electron) occurs when the water molecule is replaced by cyanide or hydrogen sulphide. Nitric oxide gives a diamagnetic complex with the reduction

3. Eickhorn, "Co-ordination Compounds in Natural Products", in "The Chemistry of the Co-ordination Compounds", edited by Bailar (Jr.), Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York, 1956, p. 725.

of iron(III) to iron(II). Carbon monoxide does not affect the activity of the enzyme, but it forms a diamagnetic covalent complex with the reduced form of the ~~peroxidase~~.

Cytochromes.—This group of enzymes resembles the peroxidases and catalases, being iron-porphyrine-protein complexes. These differ from each other in the nature of their protein component and serve as transmitter of the oxidising power of molecular oxygen to the substrate through a series of redox reactions at comparatively lower potentials which avert any injury to the cells that might otherwise arise from a single-stage reaction at a higher potential.

The iron-free prosthetic group (porphyrine c) of cytochrome c has the following structure:

Porphyrine c.

It contains two molecules of cysteine, each linked to a two-carbon side chain of the two vinyl groups of protoporphyrin, discussed before, and resembles the latter in all other respects.

Each molecule of cytochrome contains one hemin group, which is apparently bound to the protein at four places. In addition to the four nitrogen atoms of the porphyrine ring, the iron is co-ordinated to two more basic donors in the protein part, presumably the histidine imidazole^{3a}. The enzyme functions as a redox system by change of

valency of the iron due to electron transfer:

The Cysteine-cystine System.—Many redox reactions in biological systems are known to involve the cysteine-cystine transformation ($-\text{SH} \rightleftharpoons -\text{S}-\text{S}$). These substances are presumed to function as part of a protein body in the system, the oxidation reaction being catalysed by the formation of an iron complex.

In solution, iron(III) readily reacts with cysteine to give a violet colour, which fades on standing, but can be revived by repeated agitation with air till all the cysteine has been oxidised to cystine. The violet complex is believed to be a tris-(cysteine)—iron(III) complex as represented by structure(I). The catalytic oxidation of the sulphhydryl group of glutathione by iron can also be explained in a similar manner^{3b}.

Cytochrome c

3a. *Idem, ibid.*, p. 728.

3b. *Idem, ibid.*, pp. 730-31.

Molybdenum-containing Enzymes.—Molybdenum has been found to be an essential requirement for the normal growth of many plants⁴. Recent studies on the subject⁵ have demonstrated that these enzymes in the oxidised state contain the molybdenyl ion, $(MoO_2)^{2+}$, bound to a carboxylate of the protein and/or to aromatic nitrogen and phenolic oxygen of the co-enzyme (prosthetic group) or substrates. Molybdenum is a constituent of nitrate reductase in the soil and is also known to be a constituent of xanthine oxidase system of milk and of rat liver, and of the aldehyde oxidase of pig liver. But there is no evidence as yet of any molybdenum deficiency disease or symptoms in animals. The catalytic function of molybdenum in redox reactions has been attributed to the change:

in the complex-bound molybdenum.

The role of vanadium in biological processes has been reviewed by Bertrand⁶. It has been found to be an essential element for nitrifying bacteria and some species of fungi.

(b) Reactions of the Acid-base Type

Many biochemical reactions leading to the formation or dissolution of chemical bonds are catalysed by specific enzymes through complex formation by their constituent metal atoms. The metal ion can bring together two molecules between which the reaction may take place by co-ordinating with functional groups or donor atoms of the two molecules. It can thus serve as a temporary bridge between two atoms for their mutual combination. It can also accelerate the dissolution of a bond in a molecule by co-ordination with one or more donor atoms in the same. This results in the shifting of electrons towards the metal, weakening the bonds in the molecule, and thus lowering the activation energy necessary for their severance.

Degradation of Proteins.—The catalytic cleavage of chemical bonds is best illustrated by the metabolic decomposition of proteins into amino-acids through a series of stages

4. Marston, *Physiol. Rev.*, 1952, **32**, 66; "Molybdenum in Plant and Animal Nutrition", *Soil Sci.*, 1956, **81**, 159.
5. Williams, "The Biochemical Significance of Co-ordination Compounds" in "Advances in the Chemistry of Co-ordination Compounds", edited by Kirschner, The Macmillan Company, New York, 1961, p. 65.
6. Bertrand, *Bull. Am. Museum Nat. Hist.*, 1950, **94**, 407.

by several enzymes, generally known as peptidases. These proteolytic enzymes are distinguished as endopeptidases by which the large molecules of protein are first fragmented into polypeptides, which are then further degraded by aminopeptidases and carboxypeptidases into dipeptides. The former acts on the amino terminal and the latter on the carboxyl terminal of the peptide chain. The dipeptides are then finally broken up into amino-acids by dipeptidases. By means of various activation and inhibition experiments, it has been shown that the amino-, carboxy-, and di-peptidases are metal complexes and their activities depend on the metal ion leading to intermediate complex formation⁷. The dipeptidases have been found to contain metals like cobalt, manganese, zinc, and magnesium.

The structure of the cobalt(II) enzyme-glycylglycine intermediate may be formulated as follows with the cobalt atom co-ordinated with the amino-group, the peptide-nitrogen, and the carboxyl group of the substrate, besides being bound to three different positions on the enzyme protein to satisfy its co-ordination number⁸.

The complex is hydrolysed, forming glycine and regenerating the enzyme. It might also be noted that the metal ions in these enzymes are not very strongly held and are in mobile equilibrium with the protein part of the molecule which acts as a chelating agent.

Carboxylation and Decarboxylation Reactions.—Metal-containing carboxylase enzymes have been found to catalyse widely occurring reversible processes of the addition and removal of carbon dioxide through the formation of complex intermediates. The metal ions, responsible for activity of these enzymes, are usually manganese(II), magnesium(II), and iron(III).

The mechanism of the enzymic reactions for the conversion of oxalosuccinic acid to α -ketoglutaric acid, of α -ketoglutaric acid to succinic acid, and of oxalo-acetic acid to pyruvic acid may be summarised here as first formulated by Steinberger and Westheimer⁹.

7. Smith, "Enzymes and Enzyme Systems", Edsall, Cambridge, Harvard University Press, 1951, pp. 43-76; Smith and Bergmann, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1941, **138**, 789; 1944, **153**, 627.
8. Martell and Calvin, "Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compounds", Chap. 8, Prentice-Hall Inc. New York, 1952.
9. Steinberger and Westheimer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 420.

These decarboxylation reactions have been found to be catalysed by free metal ions even in the absence of protein, though the latter markedly accelerates the rate of reaction. But the metal ion alone is incapable of exerting any specific action, whereas the protein makes the enzyme specifically active for one and only one particular substrate.

Phosphorylation.—Many biochemical reactions connected with carbohydrate and nucleoprotein metabolism lead to the formation or dissolution of phosphate bonds. The enzymes, phosphatases, catalysing these reactions contain usually magnesium as a metallic constituent. The magnesium ion through the formation of complex intermediates brings together the donor and the acceptor of the phosphate. Phosphorylation of glucose by adenosine triphosphate (ATP) may be cited as an example. An idea about the structure of the complex intermediate can be obtained from the following representation:

Magnesium atom is covalently bound in an octahedral configuration with glucose, adenosine triphosphate, and the enzyme protein through chelate rings¹⁰. Phosphorus—

10. Calvin, "A Symposium on the Mechanism of Enzyme Action", edited by McElroy and Glass, Johns Hopkins Press, Baltimore, 1954.

oxygen bond is thereby labilised and the reacting molecules are brought close together. Magnesium, as is well known, forms relatively strong bonds with phosphates.

Insulin, a zinc-protein enzyme, is extensively used as a very important drug in diabetes. The mechanism of its action is not exactly known, but is believed to be related to carbohydrate phosphorylation reaction. The enzyme can combine with the diabetogenic hormone to form a complex intermediate of insulin-Zn-hormone and thus preventing the hormone from retarding phosphorylation necessary for carbohydrate metabolism. The hormone can inhibit the phosphorylation of glucose through complex formation with Mg-phosphorylase, which is thereby inactivated. Insulin removes the hormone from its field of action, when Mg-phosphorylase becomes free to catalyse the phosphorylation reaction^{11,3}. The reaction mechanism can be summarised as follows:

It has been shown that in insulin, Zn(II) is co-ordinatively bound to histidine imidazole groups of the protein^{11a}.

Actomyosin.—Another instance of the catalysis of phosphorylation reaction through complex formation is provided by the action of the metal-protein complex, the enzyme actomyosin, which plays an active role in muscular contraction. The energy for this muscular contraction is derived from the decomposition of ATP to ADP. It is believed that the contraction involves co-ordination of magnesium of actomyosin with the ATP, facilitating the cleavage of a phosphate radical¹².

The iron-catalysed cysteine-cystine reaction, previously discussed, provides an instance of bond-making through complex formation.

Exchange of Functional Groups.—There are biochemical reactions in which an exchange of functional groups occurs between the reacting molecules. Transamination is

11. Baldwin, "Dynamic Aspects of Biochemistry", Cambridge University Press, 1952, p. 413; also Ref. 3.

11a. Tanford and Epstein, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 2163, 2170.

12. Szent-Györgyi, "Chemistry of Muscular Contraction", 2nd ed., New York, Academic Press, 1951.

For detailed information on enzymatic activity pertaining to the function of metals, references may be made to the reviews on the subject by Klotz^{15a} and by Williams^{15b}.

II Storage and Transfer of Donor Molecules or Metal Ions and Transmission of Energy

Transportation of Oxygen.—The most important agent for oxygen transport in living bodies is hemoglobin. Its prosthetic group heme is iron (II) protoporphyrine, which is also co-ordinatively bound to the protein, globin. Each hemoglobin molecule is found to contain four such heme groups on the surface of its protein part, globin. In the free state the octahedral iron(II) complex heme has its two more co-ordination positions above and below the plane of the porphyrine molecule occupied by water molecules.

The magnetic moment of heme gives a value corresponding to the presence of four unpaired electrons, characteristic of Fe^{2+} ion; hence the bondings are ionic or of an outer orbital (high spin) type. The complex heme in the free state is therefore somewhat unstable and is very sensitive to oxygen, readily combining with it to form a labile oxygen complex intermediate, which changes finally to iron(III) protoporphyrine complex, hemin. Hemin also shows a magnetic moment corresponding to that of Fe^{3+} ion with five unpaired electrons. When the water molecules of heme and hemin are replaced by ammonia, amines, cyanide, etc, they give rise to very stable complexes, hemochromes and hemichromes respectively. The former are diamagnetic and the latter show a moment value corresponding to that of a covalent iron(III) complex (one unpaired electron). This results in a profound change in the iron-ligand linkage. The linkage of iron to the protein of hemoglobin is assumed to occur through an imidazole nitrogen of histidine in the polypeptide chain of the protein. Carbon monoxide can combine with heme and hemoglobin but not with hemin or proteinated hemin, whereas the cyanide ion reacts with hemin or proteinated hemin but not with heme or hemoglobin. The labile oxygen-complex intermediate of heme is stabilised, however, in hemoglobin, which is one of the important functions of protein in hemoglobin. Oxyhemoglobin and carboxyhemoglobin are both stable covalent complexes and are diamagnetic. Of the two, carboxyhemoglobin, however, is more stable and carbon monoxide can displace the co-ordinated oxygen molecule from oxyhemoglobin. The toxicity and high poisonous character of carbon monoxide arises from this, as it renders the hemoglobin

15a. Klotz, "The Mechanism of Enzyme Action", edited by McElroy and Glass, p. 257, Johns Hopkins Press, Baltimore; Williams, *Biol. Rev.*, 1953, 28, 381.

molecule incapable of performing its oxygen-carrying function. Similar action is also exerted by cyanide ion, another deadly poison^{16,17}.

One or the other of the two following configurations is now generally accepted for the structure of hemoglobin molecule as incorporating all its characteristic properties.¹⁸

Another oxygen-carrying natural product is the copper(I) protein complex, hemocyanin, which behaves like hemoglobin towards oxygen, carbon monoxide, and cyanide. It occurs in the blood of invertebrate animals. The structure of the complex is not definitely known.

Synthetic Oxygen-carrying Complexes.—Reference might be made here to the work on synthetic oxygen-carrying chelates, though they are not directly concerned with any biological process. Their studies have, however, contributed in no small measure to the elucidation of the structure and behaviour of the more complicated natural products.

The first synthetic reversible oxygen carrier, bis-salicylaldehyde-ethylenediamine-cobalt(II), was described by Pfoiffer and co-workers¹⁸. Since then a large number of its derivatives have been prepared and an intensive study on their behaviour and structure made by Calvin, Diehl, and their associates¹⁹. Reversible oxygen-carrying chelates of cobalt(II) amino-acid (histidine, histamine, lysine, etc.)²⁰ and cobalt(II) dipeptide (including glycylglycine) chelates²¹ have also been examined by several workers.

Evidence for the oxidation of cobalt(II) to cobalt(III) of the cobalt(II) dihistidine and cobalt(II) glycylglycine chelates in their irreversible oxidation products has been re-

16. Pauling and Coryell, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., U.S.*, 1930, **22**, 159, 210; Pauling, Whitney, and Felsing, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 633.

17. Ref. 3, pp. 732-35.

18. Pfoiffer, Breith, Lubbe, and Tsumaki, *Annalen*, 1933, **503**, 84.

19. Ref. 8, pp. 336-57.

20. Burk, Hearon, Caroline, and Schade, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1946, **165**, 723; Hearon, *J. Nat. Cancer Inst.*, 1948, **9**, 1; Hearon and Burk, *ibid.*, 1949, **9**, 337; Michaelis, *Arch. Biochem.*, 1947, **14**, 17.

21. Gilbert and Otey, and Price, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1948, **173**, 571.

ported from their photographic studies²². The ultraviolet spectrum of the reversibly oxygenated cobalt(II) glycylglycine was found to show an intense charge-transfer band, indicating that in their oxygenated forms the chelates may be considered as charge-transfer complexes.

A solution of iron(II) dimethylglyoxime in 50% aqueous solution of dioxane, containing bases like pyridine, ammonia, histidine, or imidazole, has been found to exhibit the phenomenon of reversible oxygen absorption²³.

A detailed discussion of the properties and structure of synthetic oxygen-carrying chelates has been made by Martell and Calvin²⁴, and a review on the subject, containing full references, has recently been published²⁵.

It might be mentioned here that a large number of metal complexes^{25a} of Schiff's bases derived from various aromatic aldehydes, amines, and amino-acids were prepared in our laboratories at the University College of Science and at the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta, but their oxygen-absorption capacity remains to be explored.

Storage of Metal Ions by Complex Formation.—Ferritin, an iron (III) protein complex, containing about 17-23% iron, has been found to serve as the store-house for this element in the body until it is needed for hemoglobin synthesis²⁶.

Copper in trace amounts has been found to be essential for the synthesis of hemoglobin and it occurs in the form of a metalloprotein, hemocuprein, in the blood cells, containing 0.34% copper. The function of hemocuprein and the role of copper in hemoglobin synthesis, are not yet definitely known²⁶.

Cyanocobalamin, the antianaemic cobalt-containing vitamin-B₁₂, has got a Co(III) porphyrine-like (corphyrine) chelate with one of the co-ordination positions of the cobalt atom being occupied by a cyanide ion on the one side and by a benzimidazole nitrogen on the other side. The benzimidazole occurs at the end of a long side chain on the corphyrine. The cyanide ion may be replaced by hydroxide through acid hydrolysis, yielding hydroxocobalamin and aquocobalamin (B_{12a}). The oxidation state (+3) of cobalt in the vitamin is deduced from its diamagnetic character. By treatment with cyanide ion both hydroxo- and aquo-cobalamin may be reconverted to cyanocobalamin (B₁₂). The vitamin is found

22. Caglioti, Silvestroni, and Furlani, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1960, **13**, 95.

23. Drake and Williams, *Nature*, 1958, **182**, 1084.

24. Ref. 19.

25. Vogt (Jr.), Faigenbaum, and Wiberley, *Chem. Rev.*, 1963, **63**, 269.

25a. Mukherjee and Ray, *this Journal*, 1955, **32**, 505, 567, 581, 604, 633.

26. Ref. 3, pp. 736-37.

in the liver, pancreas, and spleen. It functions as a co-enzyme ~~in a system~~ and can be represented as having the following skeleton structure²⁷:

Vitamin B₁₂ (skeleton)

Inside the body the valency of the cobalt atom in vitamin B₁₂ may vary from (+3) to (+1).

Chelate Complexes in Transmission of Energy.—As in the animal ~~body~~ home, an iron(II) porphyrine complex in hemoglobin of the blood, serves the purpose of oxygen transport in the body, so does chlorophyll, the green colouring matter of the plant and also a porphyrine complex containing magnesium(II), perform the function of capturing light energy (photons) and transmitting it to a system for utilisation in chemical reaction. This results in the synthesis of products essential to plant life. In the plant body chlorophyll is obviously associated with a protein part, as heme forms the prosthetic group of hemoglobin. There are various modifications of chlorophyll, differing in the side groups of the porphyrine ring. The most commonly occurring one, chlorophyll-*a*, has the structure:

Chlorophyll-*a*

The unique property of chlorophyll, *i.e.*, of capturing and transmitting light energy to a system for chemical reaction, may presumably be attributed to the nature of the metal ion and the ligand molecule, forming the structure of the complex. Magnesium, which possesses no available *d*-orbitals for strong planar bond formation, usually forms tetrahedral complexes. The porphyrine molecule, on the other hand, by its rigid structure

holds the four donor-nitrogen atoms in the same plane and thus forces any metal ion co-ordinating with it to assume a planar structure. Hence, the planar magnesium bonds in chlorophyll must be in a strained condition. The electrons constituting these bonds can therefore be readily excited by the absorption of light energy, which may be re-emitted afterwards in the form of luminiscence or transmitted to a chemical reaction system²⁸.

The biosynthesis of chlorophyll itself seems to offer features of considerable interest from the viewpoint of co-ordination chemistry. One of the essential functions of iron in plants is regarded to be the catalytic role it plays in the synthesis of chlorophyll. From this arises the importance of iron in plant nutrition. It has been suggested²⁹ that iron (III), which usually forms very stable metal chelates, acts as an organiser in the plant body, bringing together four pyrrole groups in the correct position for condensation to a cyclic planar porphyrine ring with formation of a stable iron chelate. But iron is present only in traces, whereas magnesium is present in relatively large amounts. Hence, the simultaneous push by a large number of magnesium ions and pull by a crowd of pyrrole groups for the formation of another stable porphyrine ring to enter into co-ordination with iron, displace the iron from its original porphyrine complex for the formation of a new one, and the position vacated by iron is occupied by magnesium. Iron thus plays the role of a catalyst in the biosynthesis of chlorophyll, exchanging its place, in spite of its stronger binding power, with magnesium of a weaker co-ordinating capacity. This can be represented by the following scheme:

In plant and animal bodies, as already stated, quite a large number of metallic elements are known to occur. Many of these, particularly the heavier ones, are present only in trace amounts and, for reasons stated before, form stable, soluble co-ordination or chelate complexes, either cationic or anionic. In the plant bodies the main chelating agents are generally the citrate, tartrate, malate, and various amino-acid anions. The roots of plants secrete and release small amounts of organic acids, which dissolve these metals from the soil for transport into the plant body as complex anions. For, the physiological pH, both in the plant and the animal system, is high enough to convert otherwise the simple heavy metal ions completely into their insoluble hydrolytic products. Citrate, malate, and lactate salts are generally found in the blood serum.

28. Ref. 3, pp. 740-42.

29. Chaberek and Martell, "Organic Sequestering Agents", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1959, pp. 437-42.

Use of Co-ordination or Chelate Complexes in Biological Systems

*Plant and Animal Nutrition*³⁰.—Remarkable results have been obtained in iron chlorosis of citrus and some other plants by the use of iron(III) chelates of EDTA, HEDTA, DTPA, and EHPG, depending on the pH condition of the soil.

EDTA = Ethylenediaminetetra-acetic acid;

Fe(III)—EDTA:

HEDTA = Hydroxyethylethylenediaminetri-acetic acid:

DTPA = Diethylenetriaminepenta-acetic acid:

EHPG = *NN'*-Ethylene-bis-2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)glycine:

Good results have also been reported on the use of Zn(II)-EDTA and Mn(II)-EDTA in some cases.

Iron chelate and Cu(II) chelate have also been found to give encouraging results in certain cases of animal nutrition.

Lead Poisoning and Poisoning by Radioactive Metals³¹.—Ca(II)-EDTA has been used with very satisfactory results in cases of lead poisoning. Lead is readily exchanged with calcium as Pb(II)-EDTA is much more stable than the calcium chelate. The lead chelate is non-toxic and is rapidly eliminated through the kidney. Ca(II)-EDTA has also been found quite useful in removing many radioactive rare earth and other harmful metals from the animal body.

Among other possible uses of chelate or complex formation in biological systems, mention may be made of the following³². Cholesterol deposits in the arterial system are, it is interpreted, stabilised by metal ions like Ca^{2+} ions. Use of EDTA is expected to prevent such deposition and the possible application of EDTA in the treatment of arteriosclerosis is being explored. The stability of the calcium chelate of EDTA suggests its use as an anticoagulant for blood, since blood coagulation is catalysed by calcium ion. EDTA has also been found to prevent the destruction of red blood corpuscles (hemolysis) and it is expected to be used as an effective reagent for the preparation and storage of whole blood. Some experimental work has also been carried out by a few workers with partial success for removing kidney and bladder stones by irrigation with sodium salts of EDTA. A very interesting medical use of EDTA relates to the restoration of eyesight of patients suffering from calcification opacity in the eye. Simply a local irrigation with EDTA serves as the remedy. Prolongation of the life span of sea urchin sperm by the use of EDTA has also been reported. The effect is attributed to the deactivation of zinc ions which retards the fertilization process.

Activity of Drugs³³.—Activity of certain drugs has been found to be related to their affinity for linking with metal ions for complex formation or chelation.

It is reported that in rheumatic fever, the non-chelating analogues of salicylic acid, *m*- and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acids, are relatively ineffective compared to salicylic acid. While 8-hydroxyquinoline has been found to induce diabetes mellitus in rabbits, 8-methoxyquinoline, which does not form chelate complexes, is not a diabetogenic agent. The antibacterial activity of 8-hydroxyquinoline and of its derivatives have also been found to be proportional to their capacity for binding metal ions in complex formation.

31. Ref. 29, p. 478 *et seq.*

32. Ref. 29, pp. 485-87.

33. Ref. 29, pp. 488-90; Albert *et al.*, *Biochem. J.*, 1947, 41, 534; *J. Exptl. Pathol.*, 1947, 28, 69.